

Human performance management in the tire industry: a case study

*Gestão de desempenho humano na indústria de
pneumáticos: um estudo de caso*

*Gestión del desempeño humano en la industria de
neumáticos: estudio de caso*

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Abstract:

Remote work has emerged as a consequence of generational shifts, globalization, and technological advancements, with its relevance significantly heightened during the COVID-19 pandemic. The transition from in-person to remote work created the need for accurate assessment tools to ensure sustained productivity in professional tasks. In response to this new labor landscape, this article aims to identify key elements for developing metrics to evaluate telework performance, considering the physical, psychological, and social dimensions of work activities. The research is justified by the operational demand for indicators that support organizations in managing remote work while ensuring continuity. A literature review was conducted to identify relevant concepts and practices, which were synthesized into a conceptual model, subsequently applied through a survey and validated via a case study. This study adopts a qualitative, exploratory, descriptive, and methodological approach, employing the case study as a technical procedure. The findings provide parameters for measuring employee performance in remote work contexts, indicating positive perceptions regarding social, behavioral, structural, and physical factors, while also highlighting the subjectivity of psychological aspects and discrepancies between general and individual productivity assessments.

Keywords: *Telecommuting; Performance Management; Human Resources; Tire Industry.*

Resumo: O *home office* emergiu como resultado das mudanças geracionais, da globalização e do avanço tecnológico, tendo sua importância ampliada durante a pandemia de Covid-19. Com a mudança do trabalho presencial pelo trabalho remoto, surgiu a necessidade de avaliar sua produtividade de forma precisa, garantindo produtividade nas atividades desenvolvidas. Frente a esta nova realidade do mundo do trabalho, este artigo teve como objetivo identificar elementos para o desenvolvimento de métricas que avaliem a performance no teletrabalho, levando em consideração as dimensões físicas, psicológicas e sociais das atividades desenvolvidas. A pesquisa justifica-se pela necessidade de formular indicadores que auxiliem as organizações no gerenciamento do trabalho remoto, garantindo a continuidade das tarefas. A partir da revisão de literatura, identificou-se conceitos e práticas, sendo traduzidas em um modelo conceitual, posteriormente aplicado a uma pesquisa de levantamento e validado por estudo de caso. O estudo possui abordagem qualitativa, de caráter exploratório, descritivo e metodológico, utilizando o procedimento técnico de estudo de caso. Os resultados apresentam

parâmetros para medir o desempenho de trabalhadores quando em atividades remotas. Os resultados indicaram percepções positivas nos fatores sociais, comportamentais, estruturais e físicos, embora tenha apontado subjetividade nos aspectos psicológicos e diferenças entre as avaliações gerais e individuais de produtividade.

Palavras-chave: Trabalho Remoto; Gestão de Desempenho; Recursos Humanos; Indústria de Pneumáticos.

Resumen: El teletrabajo ha surgido como resultado de los cambios generacionales, la globalización y los avances tecnológicos, adquiriendo una relevancia aún mayor durante la pandemia de Covid-19. La transición del trabajo presencial al remoto generó la necesidad de evaluar la productividad de manera precisa, con el fin de asegurar el rendimiento en las tareas desarrolladas. Ante este nuevo escenario laboral, el presente artículo tiene como objetivo identificar elementos clave para el desarrollo de métricas que permitan evaluar el desempeño en el teletrabajo, considerando las dimensiones físicas, psicológicas y sociales de las actividades realizadas. La investigación se justifica por la necesidad de formular indicadores que apoyen a las organizaciones en la gestión del trabajo a distancia, garantizando la continuidad operativa. A partir de una revisión de la literatura, se identificaron conceptos y prácticas que fueron traducidos en un modelo conceptual, posteriormente aplicado mediante una encuesta y validado a través de un estudio de caso. El estudio adopta un enfoque cualitativo, de carácter exploratorio, descriptivo y metodológico, utilizando el estudio de caso como procedimiento técnico. Los resultados presentan parámetros para medir el rendimiento de los trabajadores en contextos de trabajo remoto, señalando percepciones positivas en los factores sociales, conductuales, estructurales y físicos, aunque también revelan la subjetividad de los aspectos psicológicos y diferencias entre las evaluaciones generales e individuales de productividad.

Palabras clave: Trabajo remoto; Gestión del desempeño; Recursos humanos; Industria de neumáticos.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the National Tire Industry Association – NTIA (*Associação Nacional da Indústria de Pneumáticos - ANIP*), total tire sales decreased 8.2% in 2023 compared to 2022, falling from 56.64 million to 51.97 million units (NTIA, 2024). This reduction highlights the need for internal measures to maintain service quality, contain costs, and avoid layoffs. In this context, teleworking, or home office, presents itself as a strategic alternative, characterized by the remote performance of work activities supported by communication technologies (Taschetto; Froehlich, 2019).

The concept of telework, according to the International Labor Organization (ILO), encompasses activities carried out in locations distant from the central office or production center, enabling physical separation and involving the use of facilitating communication technologies (ILO, 2009). According to Costa (2004), telework can be organized in several ways, namely: home office, when carried out at the teleworker's home; mobile telework, carried out by people in constant movement, such as traveling or visiting clients; satellite offices, where teleworkers travel to company branches located outside large urban centers; and telecenters, shared offices equipped with technological resources, used by several companies or individuals for specific periods.

Working from home offers the opportunity to perform activities remotely, using communication equipment and technologies. While not necessarily performed at home, teleworking often occurs at the worker's home, characterizing what is commonly known as a home office. Workplace flexibility has become an increasingly popular and viable option in various sectors and professional contexts (Nascimento; Nascimento, 2014). The adoption of this work model impacts both organizations and the lives of workers, resulting in effects that reverberate throughout society, with advantages and disadvantages for all parties mentioned (Rodrigues, 2011).

For workers, working from home offers advantages such as increased productivity, reduced absenteeism and stress-related illnesses, and increased job satisfaction. This satisfaction is attributed to the improved working conditions at home compared to a traditional work environment, as well as the autonomy and flexible working hours provided by telecommuting. Autonomy and independence to perform tasks allow workers to manage their time and potentially offer their services to other companies, expanding their job opportunities (Kugelmass, 1996; Silva, 2004; Rodrigues, 2011). Disadvantages for workers include distractions and temptations, isolation, procrastination, lack of technical support, prejudice, household noise, and disorganized workspace (Brik; Brik, 2013).

For society and the government, working from home offers advantages such as job creation, particularly in sectors geared toward the globalized market, reducing unemployment rates and increasing income. It also contributes to reducing congestion, pollution, and the exclusion of people with disabilities through their inclusion in the labor market. However, there are disadvantages, such as the precariousness of labor relations due to a lack of adequate oversight,

impacts on worker health due to inadequate ergonomic conditions, and the possibility of exploiting cheap labor through international subcontracting, making it challenging to monitor established labor relations (Mello, 2011; Rodrigues; 2011).

For companies, working from home offers advantages such as reduced costs associated with maintaining physical workspaces, allowing resources to be directed toward improving organizational productivity. Flexible working hours and geographic location enable continuous operations, while the global selection of professionals expands the pool of available talent. This approach reduces turnover and absenteeism, promoting better use of time and production resources (Silva, 2004; Rodrigues, 2011).

On the other hand, the disadvantages are evident in the challenges of the recruitment and selection process, which require identifying the right profile and overcoming management resistance to change. There are costs associated with its implementation, such as investments in technology and training, and technological incompatibility can hinder assertive communication. Data security is also a concern, as is the potential decline in productivity and team spirit among employees who work from home, which reflects a primary concern for organizations regarding team control (Brik; Brik, 2013).

Considering the growing demand for flexible work typologies driven by the global Covid-19 pandemic, in parallel with the need for companies to find ways to manage the activities of their employees who work remotely, it becomes necessary to address performance indicators in human resources, specifically in measuring the productivity of employees who do not work in person, with a focus on the quality of the administrative tasks under their responsibility (Barino; Santos, 2023).

Based on the premise that working from home involves challenges such as self-management of time, technological dependence, individual monitoring, punctuality in deliveries, and working conditions (Fundação Dom Cabral, 2020), this article aimed to identify metrics to assess performance in remote work. The research is justified by the need to balance employee well-being with the organization's interest in maximizing productivity and quality, considering the physical, psychological, and social dimensions of the work environment (Chiavenato, 1999). The relevance of the study lies in the fact that organizations operate as social systems, where member commitment impacts their performance (Simon, 1965).

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

2.1 The evolution of the Human Resources area

The origins of Human Resource Management (HR) date back to the academic attempt, in the late 19th century, to understand the "labor question" during the emergence of wage labor in the industrialization era. This period witnessed the adoption of the principles of Taylorism and Fordism by large corporations,

followed by the influence of the School of Human Relations in the mid-20th century. Taylor, in his publications between 1903 and 1906, sought to optimize production processes, while Fayol, in 1916, introduced the concept of the division of managerial functions, highlighting planning, organization, coordination, command, and control as fundamental components of organizational management (Amorim; Comini; Fischer, 2019).

In the 1920s, the Human Relations movement emerged, shifting the administrative paradigm by focusing on transforming employee-employer relationships. While previously coercion and autocracy had predominated in management, the new model aimed to increase productivity through conflict resolution and consideration of employees' individual needs. Despite the challenges faced due to a lack of preparation for change, the movement progressed to the Behaviorism phase, based on the study of human behavior and the belief that job satisfaction would lead to improvements (Viscaino; Estork, 2007).

Viscaino and Estork (2007) also highlighted that in the 1940s, pioneering studies on leadership, workplace democracy, and human motivation emerged, leading to a shift in the role of the personnel manager. The manager became responsible for both employee well-being and the organization's interests, given the emergence of legal and union issues. This evolution resulted in the transformation of the role from Personnel Manager to HR Manager in the 1950s, and later, in the 1960s, in the creation of the position of Industrial Relations Manager to distinguish administrative responsibilities from human and relational issues.

Inherent to the Brazilian labor market, the evolution of the professional profile of the HR worker is categorized into five distinct phases, each marked by specific emphases and contexts, namely:

- a) Accounting Phase (19th century until the beginning of the 1930s): Concentration on organizational costs and accounting records of labor, the initial milestone of personnel management;
- b) Legal Phase (1930s to 1950s): Emphasis on compliance with labor legislation after the creation of the CLT and the introduction of the role of Chief of Personnel to ensure legal compliance;
- c) Technician Phase (1950s to 1965): Inclusion of the Industrial Relations Manager due to the expansion of the automobile industry and expansion of HR responsibilities, such as recruitment and safety;
- d) Administrative Phase (1965 to 1985): Transformation in labor relations with the "new unionism" and change to a humanistic approach, renaming the position to HR Manager;
- e) Strategic Phase (Mid-1980s onwards): Integration of strategic planning programs into HR practices and elevation of the role of the HR Manager to a strategic level.

In the Brazilian context, Human Resources Management (HR) is strongly influenced by the theories of the Human Relations School, which emerged in the 1930s, as corroborated by Amorim, Comini, and Fischer (2019). These theories highlight the importance of employee well-being and communication between managers and subordinates. Over the following decades, especially from the 1960s onward, HRM gradually became recognized as a strategic area in organizations. With the arrival of the 1990s and the advent of globalization and the opening of the Brazilian economy, there was a growing emphasis on business competitiveness, resulting in the professionalization of the HRM field.

The origins of studies related to HR, Human Resources, and Personnel Management in Brazil date back to the 1940s, with their consolidation beginning in the 1950s, with the establishment of the first educational institutions focused on business administration and management. During this period, knowledge about personnel management spread, influenced by the theories of the School of Human Relations, which prioritized interpersonal interactions and employee well-being in the workplace. In the transition from the 1970s to the 1980s, the discipline gained even more prominence due to the growing focus on labor issues in Brazil, resulting in the development of the Human Resources field (Bianchi; Quishida; Foroni, 2017).

The evolution of PM studies in Brazil reflects a reorientation to align policies and strategies with a new scenario marked by market openness, growing entrepreneurship, increased competition, and the pursuit of innovation, quality, and efficiency. In this context, attracting, training, valuing, and retaining talent have assumed fundamental strategic importance in the new millennium, shaping the principles, foundations, and concepts of modern PM (Wood Júnior; Tonelli; Cooke, 2011).

The evolution of HR reflects a series of theoretical and historical changes, from the Taylorist and Fordist eras to the focus on human relations and the professionalization of the field. Initially focused on accounting and legal aspects, HR management now emphasizes the strategy of attracting, training, and retaining talent to meet market innovation demands (Barino *et al*, 2024). Chiavenato (1999) emphasizes that HRM is essential to achieving organizational and individual objectives, emphasizing its functional, strategic, and collaborative role within the corporate structure.

2.2 Performance indicators in Human Resources

Performance indicators, according to Padoveze (2016), consist of a set of financial and non-financial measures established by management. These serve as targets to be achieved or exceeded to monitor the performance of the Company and divisional managers. Performance evaluation, according to Dutra (2003), involves assigning value to what an organization considers relevant to its strategic objectives; that is, the criteria must be aligned with the Company's competitive strategy.

Currently, there is growing pressure on Human Resources departments to demonstrate their value in an increasingly competitive and cost-constrained

business environment. The growing emphasis on organizational change processes, quality programs, increased productivity, and the implementation of HR strategies, along with the need to improve the use of information systems and strengthen partnerships with leadership, has intensified the demand for measuring HR's impact (Srimannarayana, 2010). Therefore, the increased relevance of the HR function has driven the need for accountability, resulting in greater organizational responsibility, defined as accountability, which implies the obligation to account for the results achieved (Nakagawa, 1993).

Human Resources Performance Indicators are subject to various definitions, all converging on their necessity and potential for generating action plans for business improvements. These indicators are essential for guiding the organization in its pursuit of value creation through its operations (Costa; Faria, 2007). These indicators must be aligned with the Company's strategy and translated clearly and coherently. Given that employees represent one of an organization's most important assets, HR indicators must be concrete and have specific targets, capable of quantifying results in financial terms and indicating productive performance.

For human resource management, it is essential to consider indicators that offer relevant metrics to support managers' decisions, positioning them strategically within the organization. Indicators commonly found in the literature and used by companies include:

- a) Absenteeism: unjustified absence of employees from work, which can be influenced by organizational factors such as management problems, poor integration, and poor working conditions. Its causes include an unstable organizational climate and recruitment failures, and its consequences can affect turnover, since improving the conditions that cause absenteeism can increase the Company's productivity and profits (Chiavenato, 2012);
- b) HeadCount: a baseline indicator for developing other indicators in human resource management, which can be presented in various formats, such as segmentation by gender, position, and area. Although economic and financial aspects are decisive in determining the size of the workforce, other factors must also be considered (Bancalero, 2006);
- c) Turnover: Employee turnover in an organization encompasses both entry and exit movements. Factors that can increase turnover include recruitment and selection, low commitment, organizational climate, unclear internal policies, professional development, leadership, lack of challenges, inadequate compensation, and poorly applied benefits (Pomi, 2005);
- d) Recruitment and selection: the process of identifying and attracting qualified candidates for vacancies within an organization, while selection is the process of selecting candidates who possess the necessary skills and characteristics for the position (Chiavenato, 2012). Recruitment can be internal, filling vacancies with existing employees to promote professional development and leverage prior knowledge, or external,

seeking new talent to enrich the team's diversity and expertise (França, 2007);

- e) Training and development: indicators used to evaluate employee training programs. They allow Human Resources and leadership to analyze the results of development initiatives, identifying strengths and weaknesses. These analyses enable more informed decisions aligned with the organization's strategic objectives (França, 2007). Currently, the most common term in the corporate environment is "Corporate Education";
- f) Organizational climate survey: assesses the work environment and employees' perceptions of it, helping to identify whether the environment is positive and motivating or whether there are issues that may affect well-being and productivity. By monitoring the organizational climate, companies can better understand employee needs and concerns and take steps to improve satisfaction and promote a healthier and more productive environment (Souza, 2014);
- g) Performance appraisal: a tool that allows you to understand the internal dynamics of the organization and employee performance, identifying their needs. It helps identify areas where HR is not meeting expectations, allowing the Company to direct recruitment efforts to fill critical gaps. Furthermore, it motivates employees to achieve their goals by providing guidance and encouraging self-development (Bohlander; Snell, 2010).

The interconnection between performance indicators is crucial for human resource management. Absenteeism and turnover reflect organizational health and employee engagement, influenced by factors such as organizational climate and recruitment practices. Proper recruitment and selection ensure a match between talent and company demands, while training and development promote continuous skill development. Climate surveys identify opportunities for improvement in the workplace. Performance evaluations guide recruitment, motivation, and development strategies, driving organizational success.

2.3 Productivity assessment models in the workplace

Work activity evaluation, both in academic and business literature, presents different methodologies for assessing employee performance, based on the premises of their core business activity, measuring productivity in their activities to benefit the Company. In the context of People Management, the tools summarized in Table 1 stand out.

The integration of business and academic-scientific literature, as shown in Table 1, offers several advantages. First, it allows for the practical application of theories in real business environments, increasing the relevance of academic studies. It also provides a holistic view of organizational problems, combining theory and practice, and offers innovative solutions to contemporary business challenges. Integration facilitates the dissemination of knowledge between professionals and academics, fostering greater collaboration. Finally, it contributes to the development of business management practices and policies based on evidence and solid theoretical foundations.

Table 1 - Main existing productivity assessment tools (part 1).

Instrument	Application	Reference
Human performance is influenced by individual variables such as age, length of service, and the nature of the assignments, as well as factors related to the task and the context in which the work is performed. This performance, directly linked to productivity and work effectiveness, reflects both personal and professional characteristics and the environment in which the individual works.	According to the organization's needs.	Coelho Junior (2011).
Affective commitment emerges as a mediating factor in different work contexts, as evidenced by studies on intentions to leave the Company, organizational justice, and performance. From this perspective, it is assumed that affective commitment acts as a mediator between the perception of organizational justice and performance in remote work.	The theoretical model postulates a direct effect of the perception of organizational justice and affective commitment on performance in the home office, in addition to an indirect effect of affective commitment on the relationship between the perception of organizational justice and performance, controlled by variables such as gender, age, time in the position and time working in <i>the</i> home office.	Tetteh; Osafo; Ansah-Nyarko; Amponsah-Tawiah (2019).
Instrument	Application	Reference
Performance Evaluation for <i>the</i> home office.	What should be done = expected results equivalent to goals	Coblue (2021).
Assessment of task delegation for home office workers.	How it should be done = expected behavior + skills	Coblue (2021).
Creative performance evaluation.	Creative performance = creative self-efficacy + intrinsic motivation = creative performance	Sangsuk; Siriparp (2015); Tierney; Farmer (2002); Utman (1997); Amabile (1996).
Objectives and Key Results (OKR).	Used to align the team at the organizational level and centralize the approach, aiming for synergy in the pursuit of shared goals.	Niven; Lamorte (2016).

Source: Compiled by the authors (2025).

Table 1 - Main existing productivity assessment tools (part 2).

Waterfall.	Employment of agile methodologies focused on improving communication through accessible online resources, where the systems employed provide productivity metrics, such as usability analysis and monitoring of tool usage time and interaction in online chats.	Justin; Ferry; Frollini (2021).
SMART Methodology.	Monitors and tracks daily activities, distinguishing between achievable and unachievable activities, without compromising productivity.	De Souza Junior, (2021).

Source: Compiled by the authors (2025).

3. METHOD

This article adopted a qualitative, exploratory, descriptive, and methodological approach, utilizing the case study technique. The research methods are described below:

- a) Scholar database with the help of Publish or Perish software, using the following search terms: "Performance Management," "Remote Work," and "Performance Indicators." For documentary research, we used grey literature, a field within information science that addresses the generation, dissemination, and access to various types of documents from various sources, such as government, academic, business, and organizational. For this purpose, we consulted the Google search engine. This strategy is justified by the need to address both academic and business literature.
- b) data collection in the target survey, based on documents provided by the Company;
- c) development of the conceptual model, based on the results of the literature review;
- d) After creating and administering the questionnaire, which was based on the conceptual model developed, the questionnaire was distributed to the Human Resources department of the target company in two rounds. Because this is an opinion poll without identifying the participants, submission to the Ethics Committee is not required, as provided for in the sole paragraph of Article 1 of Resolution No. 510 of April 7, 2016, which excludes from evaluation by the CEP/CONEP system public opinion polls conducted without identifying the respondents.
- e) Conducting a case study following Yin's (2017) protocol, which includes: defining and delimiting the case; selecting cases and data; preparing,

collecting, and analyzing data; and preparing the report. The analysis will be conducted using the Miles, Huberman, and Saldaña (2014) method, which involves data condensation, visual representation, and critical review of conclusions, ensuring a comprehensive and accurate analysis. The validity of the case study is assessed by the interpretative criterion, which verifies whether the observation adequately reflects the object of investigation (Croom, 2005).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

home office performance evaluation model

Home Office Worker Performance Evaluation Model, the following parameters were extracted from the literature:

- a) qualitative: age, time at the Company, time in the current position, nature of duties, type of task performed, performance expectations, skills, creativity, motivation, proactivity, communication, availability, receptiveness, autonomy, consistency, posture and ethics.
- b) quantitative: number of tasks completed, online time, request response time, average time to complete tasks, number of errors and rework, communication response time, presence in online meetings, use of shared tools for group work, time available to help colleagues.

After extracting data from the literature, a survey was sent to the Company's target Human Resources *team* to assess and validate the information. People in the following positions were interviewed: Human Resources Director, Human Resources Manager, Training and Development Coordinator, Human Resources Department Coordinator, Benefits Supervisor, and Recruitment and Selection Leader. The results of this survey are presented in Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1 - Result of survey research on qualitative elements.

Os seguintes aspectos qualitativos são observados nos trabalhadores a qual gerencio quando em regime de Home Office:

6 respostas

Source: Research results (2025).

Figure 2 - Results of survey research on quantitative elements.

Os seguintes aspectos quantitativos são observados nos trabalhadores a qual gerencio quando em regime de Home Office:

6 respostas

Source: Research results (2025).

Based on the results, the following parameters were considered to be applied in formulating the performance measure for the home office:

- qualitative parameters: type of task performed, creativity, motivation, proactivity, communication, availability, receptiveness, autonomy, consistency, posture and ethics.
- quantitative parameters: request response time, average time to complete tasks, number of errors and rework, communication response time, and presence in online meetings.

These items are represented from the conceptual model contained in Figure 3.

Home office evaluation parameters.

Source: The authors (2025).

In the model, the yellow arrows represent the input elements, which are the initial factors that feed the process. The black square highlights the set that will be analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively, that is, the object of evaluation. The green arrow indicates the output movement, directing these elements to the pink circle, which symbolizes the combination of these factors, resulting in the performance evaluation.

home office performance evaluation model

Established in 1871, the Company targeted by the study develops innovative technologies and services for sustainable and connected mobility. With a history dating back to its beginnings in Hanover, Germany, the Company offers safe and affordable solutions for vehicles, machinery, traffic, and transportation. With over 190,000 employees across 58 countries and markets, it excels in tire production, with 24 production and development sites globally.

Its history began with the manufacture of rubber products. Over the years, it has made several breakthroughs in the automotive industry, from the first tires without tread patterns to the production of non-slip tires and removable rims. Over the decades, it has innovated and reinvented itself by producing and introducing rubber products such as conveyor belts, truck springs, radial and eco-friendly tires, as well as key technologies for green automotive systems.

The group is subdivided into two areas and comprises five distinct divisions: one focuses on technologies for vehicle safety and dynamics; another offers solutions for current and future engines; there is also a division dedicated to vehicle information management; another that offers a variety of tires for different applications; and a final one that develops parts and systems for the automotive industry and other key areas.

Its industrial operations in Brazil date back to its tire manufacturing plant, officially opened on April 5, 2006. This is recognized as one of the organization's most advanced facilities, occupying a built area of 182,000 m² on an 800,000 m² site, employing over 2,300 direct workers. The group operates in the states of Rio de Janeiro, São Paulo, and Bahia, with factories and brand representative offices.

This excerpt describes the positions to be evaluated within the organizational structure: i) training analyst, reporting to the training and development coordinator; ii) HR analyst (payroll), reporting to the HR coordinator; iii) HR assistant, reporting directly to the benefits supervisor; and iv) recruitment leader, reporting to the human resources manager. These roles are detailed in Table 2 below.

The case study was conducted over two weeks in April 2024: the first week, from April 15 to 19, involved in-person productivity assessments, while the following week, from April 22 to 26, consisted of remote activities. The activities performed and assessed according to the conceptual model are detailed in Table 3.

Questionnaires were sent to the heads of the target human resources subsystem to evaluate employees during the first two weeks, the first covering in-person work and the second covering remote work. The results of the factors evaluated were analyzed in their entirety after the graphs generated from the responses were displayed, rather than after each graph. This ensures greater conciseness in the inferences made.

Table 2 - Description of activities of the functions targeted by analysis (part 1).

Human Resources Analyst (Payroll)	
Mission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Payroll Analyst's mission is to accurately and timely complete assigned processes to support a positive employee experience across all payroll execution issues. Accurate data validation is essential.
Achievements expected	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produce payroll payments using the payroll management system promptly, in accordance with the Company's compensation policies, quality and control guidelines, and legislation and regulatory requirements. • Process employee absences to ensure correct accounting of payroll exceptions. • Professional resolution of payroll discrepancies and incoming queries. • Management of alerts for discovered non-compliance or data quality issues. • Payroll documentation is organized and filed in accordance with Company and regulatory guidelines.
Training and Development Analyst	
Mission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports the Learning and Development organization by ensuring accurate and timely coordination of development activities. Analyzes data to answer end-user questions and presents the information most productively. Supports the course leader with course and administrative requirements.
Expected achievements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Learning & Development</i> offering is functional and readily available to end users. • Employee development records are accurate and up to date. • Assists in organizing training with logistical needs. • Reporting and analysis of key L&D data assessments. • Assists in the development of training plans. • Assists with departmental auditing needs. • Acts as a departmental resource to identify and analyze IT concerns related to L&D functionality.

Source: Company targeted by the study (2025).

Table 2 - Description of activities of the functions targeted by analysis (part 2).

Recruitment Leader	
Mission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Attract, identify, recruit and integrate talent in line with the needs and ambitions expressed by the group's entities within the desired timeframe.
Expected achievements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Positions corresponding to the expressed needs (required professional and behavioral skills) of managers and Proximity Development Partners are filled within the desired timeframe, in line with the group's diversity guidelines. ● The Company's attractiveness, through the Employer Brand and hiring plans, allows it to attract suitable applications for the targeted talents (quantitative and qualitative). ● All stages of the recruitment process, with all people involved, are implemented in accordance with current local legislation and based on internal guidelines and the six HR policies.
Benefits Assistant	
Mission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ensure accurate administration of company benefits, ensuring a positive employee experience. Accurate data management is crucial to the success of this mission.
Expected achievements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Management of benefits, including health insurance, transportation vouchers, and others, in accordance with company policies and regulations. ● Timely processing of benefits, ensuring compliance with relevant legislation and regulations. ● Proactive resolution of benefits-related issues. ● Management of alerts for non-compliance or data quality issues. ● Proper maintenance and archiving of benefits documentation in compliance with internal and external regulations.

Source: Company targeted by the study (2025).

Table 3 - Weekly routine of activities for the positions evaluated.

Week 1					
	15/04	16/04	17/04	18/04	19/04
Analyst training	Preparation of materials	Training of new employees	Content review	Preparation of assessments	Post-training feedback
Human Resources Analyst (payroll)	Payroll closing	Analysis of requested benefits	Adjustments to releases	Tax verification	Issuing pay slips
Human Resources Assistant (Benefits)	Report preparation	Employee support regarding benefits	Negotiation with suppliers	Registration update	Policy update
Recruitment and selection leader	Strategy planning	Resume screening and interview scheduling	Individual interviews	Profile and skills analysis	Reporting
Week 2					
	22/04	23/04	24/04	25/04	26/04
Training Analyst	Development of new courses	Review of procedures	Training planning	Preparation of the impact report	Feedback and course adjustments
Human Resources Analyst (Payroll)	Indicator analysis	Employee support	Review of calculations	Overtime and bank analysis	Optimization planning
Human Resources Assistant (Benefits)	Evaluation of new suppliers	Preparation of proposals	Service requests	Training new assistants	Review of contracts and partnerships
Recruitment and selection leader	Reporting	Meeting with managers	Performance analysis	Process evaluation	Identification of improvements

Source: Prepared from data provided by the target company (2025).

Graph 1 - Social Factors.

Graph 2 - Psychological factors.

Chart 3 - Behavioral factors.

Graph 4 – Structural factors.

Graph 5 - Physical factors.

Chart 6 - Personal skills.

Graph 7 - Productivity assessment.

The overall assessment of social, psychological, behavioral, structural, physical, and personal skills factors reveals a positive perception, both in-person and remotely. However, there is a predominance of non-perception in some cases, especially regarding psychological factors, due to their subjective nature. Behavioral factors are consistently rated as good, followed by fair or non-perceived assessments. Structural factors are rated positively, with the remaining items considered insignificant. The analysis of physical factors shows a predominance of positive assessments, with little difference in relation to the non-assessed items.

Personal skills are mostly rated as good, followed by non-assessed items. Regarding productivity, the overall assessment is positive, with a predominance of "good" ratings, followed by "average" ratings. In individual assessments, by position held, the performance assessment contrasts with the overall assessment, reflecting each employee's specific perception.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The objective of this article was to present a conceptual model for developing a performance appraisal method for employees working from home. Initially, a literature review was conducted to provide a technical basis for the study, addressing topics related to the evolution of the field of human resources management, performance indicators, and existing tools in the literature on the performance appraisal of employees working from home. This conceptual framework allows us to understand the needs inherent to this specific business sector.

Subsequently, the case study was undertaken based on the conceptual model developed from existing literature. Using qualitative and quantitative elements, forms were created and sent to managers of the areas subject to evaluation to

record their impressions. This evaluation was conducted over two weeks of activities, the first of which was in-person, followed by the second of remote work.

The results indicate a slight lack of control on the part of the Company in writing explicit rules for the home office regime, even though it fully adheres to the Company's culture. This impression stems from managers' lack of knowledge of the physical infrastructure and other determining factors for conducting activities. To correct these issues, the Company's management must intervene with the departments, with the participation of the health and safety and human resources departments, identifying needs and writing specific policies to be followed.

As a proposal for future studies, we suggest reviewing and expanding the conceptual model designed for other areas of knowledge.

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